

THE INFLUENCE OF UNCUT EDGES ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIAXIAL BRAIDED/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Mauro Ussorio, Massimo Durante, Ignazio Crivelli Visconti and Antonio Langella

*Department of Materials and Production Engineering, University of Naples "Federico II"
Piazzale V. Tecchio, 80 – 80125 Naples, ITALY*

SUMMARY: Infusion impregnation of dry textile preforms is recently subjected to extensive research aimed at investigating manufacture and material cost-reducing technologies for advanced structural applications. Among the several textile preforms available commercially, braided fabrics are largely studied for structural use. The influence of braided fabric edges on the mechanical performance of composite parts manufactured by an infusion process has been experimentally investigated in the present work. The relative amount of edge regions in comparison to the overall part volume has been varied by manufacturing biaxial braided carbon/epoxy specimens of different aspect ratios. Specimens with cut-off fabric edges have also been manufactured and tested. Specimens with higher ratios of edge regions compared to the overall volume showed better tensile and flexural performance in terms of elastic moduli and maximum stresses. A very different failure behaviour has been shown by specimens with intact fabric edges in comparison to specimens with cut-off edges.

KEYWORDS: braided fabric, textile preform, edge effect, mechanical properties, RIFT technology, failure modes

INTRODUCTION

The high manufacturing costs connected with the operation of advanced composite material production processes involving the use of pre-pregs and autoclave have stimulated extensive studies on alternative technological routes in recent years. Processes based on the impregnation of dry reinforcement preforms by liquid resin transfer mechanisms provide the opportunity to produce good quality elements with sensitively lower costs. This is partly due to the use of cheaper raw materials than pre-pregs, such as commercial textile preforms. Such preforms for reinforcing composite materials are now available with several different fibre architectures. Some architectures, such as braided fabrics, are a viable means to design and manufacture composite material elements for structural applications. In fact, thanks to a very little fibre crimping, the architectures of this type are capable of transferring a very large fraction of the fibre mechanical properties to the final composite material [1].

The yarn interlacing and fibre crimping present in textile preforms and in the resulting composite materials gives rise to the need for theoretical tools enabling a correct design activity with textile reinforced composites. Such tools have to be built through the modelling of the material thermo-mechanical properties. As for all types of composites, this behaviour is strongly influenced by the microstructure of the material. Hence, the geometrical features of

any fibre architecture plays a leading role in the modelling of textile composites, being the base for the development of a mechanical model. In the case of braided reinforced composites, it is well known that the reinforcement architecture consists of different regions, *i.e.* surface and edge regions for 2D fabric reinforcements[2, 3]. In modelling activities, these regions correspond to the surface and corner regions of 3D braided preforms, which are also characterised by an inside region that is absent in 2D fabrics. By using 2D fabrics, composite elements may either be manufactured by cutting the edge regions off or by keeping the edges uncut, and this has a considerable effect on the mechanical properties of the elements (see e.g. [4]). Existing literature shows a lack of experimental information concerning the extent to which the presence of intact fabric edges in the composite part manufactured may influence the mechanical performance, especially depending on the part dimensions. In fact, the relative dimensions of the edge regions in comparison to the overall part dimension are reasonably expected to produce a quantitatively different effect on the final mechanical properties of the composite part. A comprehensive model of braided composite materials would include a consideration of this effect based both on theoretical aspects and on experimental data.

The present work addresses the effect of edge keeping on the mechanical properties of a carbon fibre biaxial braided fabric reinforced epoxy composite laminate from an experimental point of view. The aspect ratio of composite specimen is varied to investigate the effect of different relative amounts of edge and surface regions in the volume of composite parts on the final mechanical properties of a part. Important design and manufacture implications may be derived on the use of braided reinforced composites as a consequence of such edge effects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The tests carried out in this work were mainly aimed at investigating the effect produced by keeping or eliminating the fabric edges on the mechanical properties shown by biaxial braided fabric reinforced epoxy composite materials. In all cases, the matrix used was a bi-component epoxy resin SX-10 produced by Mates (Italy), while the reinforcement preforms consisted of a carbon fibre biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ braided fabric produced by A&P Technology, Cincinnati – OH (U.S.A.). The fabric weight per unit area was 505.2gm^{-2} corresponding to a weight of 161.0gm^{-1} per unit length of a sleeve.

Four separate types of composite specimens were manufactured. The specimen manufacturing technology used was an infusion process based on the Resin Infusion under Flexible Tool (RIFT) scheme, whose details were reported elsewhere [5]. In this process the liquid thermosetting resin impregnation of dry fibre preforms takes place at room temperature and is vacuum-assisted; no additional pressure is applied during impregnation and curing, with the latter being completed after 24 hours at room temperature. Final fibre volume content of the parts manufactured by the mentioned process and component materials was of $50\pm 2\%$. Three classes of specimens had intact edges of the reinforcement, while the fourth class had a reinforcement with edges cut. The three classes of specimens were distinguished on the basis of the specimens' geometrical aspect ratio. In fact, in order to investigate the influence of fabric edges on the material's mechanical properties, the relative amount of edge reinforcement and inner reinforcement had to be varied. This was achieved by keeping the specimen length constant at a value of 300mm and increasing the specimen width from one class to another. The braided sleeves used were 155mm wide when squeezed to assume a plane geometry, so as to create a double-layer reinforcement ply. These were then repeatedly folded to produce reinforcement preforms of individual specimens, named 'folded' in the following. By varying the number of folds, the specimen width was changed, so producing the first three classes of specimens, each characterized by one value of the geometrical aspect

ratio. Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram indicating the shape and dimensions of the specimen reinforcement for the three classes of ‘folded’ specimens. Preform manufacturing was completed by a manual stitching process aimed at providing the reinforcement with the necessary shape-keeping capability prior to impregnation. This stitching had a completely non-structural function, being operated by using a cotton yarn whose mechanical properties can reasonably be neglected in comparison to the properties provided by the carbon fibre braids.

Figure 1: Schematic showing the preform stitching for the three classes of folded specimens (cross-sectional view).

Figure 2. Stitching pattern on a biaxial braided fabric: the stitching points are arranged in a two-dimensional square array and are 2mm spaced.

The fourth class of specimens was given by the edge-less specimens. In order to obtain tensile and bending specimens with cut edges, a composite plate was manufactured by the same RIFT process operated for the ‘folded’ specimens. Five braided layers, corresponding to a total of ten plies, were stacked to manufacture these preforms. The stack was then stitched, similarly to what described for the ‘folded’ specimens, with a non structural cotton yarn with a square pattern, as shown in Figure 2.

After impregnating the stack, a composite plate of 155mm×300mm was obtained. Tensile and bending specimens were cut from the plate by using a diamond saw. The width of these specimens was fixed at about 30mm, so the specimens were geometrically identical to the first class of ‘folded’ specimens. All these specimens will be called ‘cut’ in the text following.

Mechanical testing was carried out on all specimens under quasi-static loading. Tensile tests were executed by using a PC-controlled servo-hydraulic universal testing machine MTS 810 equipped with a 500kN load cell, while three-point bending tests were run by a computer-controlled MTS RT/50 machine for quasi-static tests equipped with a 50kN load cell. Results of these tests and a discussion upon them is reported in the following section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical Properties of ‘Folded’ and ‘Cut’ materials

The mechanical behaviour of the different specimens tested under uniaxial tensile load is described by the stress-strain diagrams shown in Figure 3(a). Each one of the curves refers to cut specimens and to folded specimens with different aspect ratios. The main aspect to be noticed is that the presence of fabric edge regions in the ‘folded’ specimens returns a considerably different shape of the stress-strain curves from the shape of the ‘cut’ specimens’ curve.

Figure 3. (a) Tensile stress-strain response of cut and folded specimens having different aspect ratios.

(b) Bending moment-displacement response of cut and folded specimens having identical aspect ratio = 6.67 (red line = folded; black line = cut).

After the initial linear segment representative of the elastic behaviour, obviously present in all materials, the curves of the folded specimens show a qualitatively different behaviour with respect to the curve of the cut specimens. For all the curves referring to folded specimens, at the end of the linear region the diagram becomes curved up to a peak, which represents the maximum stress reached by this material. In correspondence of this point, damage in the material is started in the form of delaminations between the plies formed by the fabric folds. A descending segment of the diagram follows, indicating that the damage is spreading over the larger areas of the material. The next region of the diagram is constant stress region

present over a range of about 8% strain. In the straining phase represented by this constant stress trend, the phenomenon taking place in the material behaviour is a re-orientation of fibre yarns towards a reduction of the initial angle to the load direction. This re-orientation is free of the initial matrix obstacle present in the elastic region and is only contrasted by the matrix material embedding the fabric yarns in each ply. The re-orientation of fibres occurring in this region is capable of inducing very large deformations of the specimen, resulting in the wide strain range experienced by the material. The final region of the diagram is a quick drop of the curve, signalling the end of the specimen capability to bear the applied load. In this phase the final failure of the material takes place and the test is finished.

In the curve of the cut specimens, after this non-linear increase of the stress-strain diagram, there exist a ‘knee’ segment, in which a slower stress increase as a function of the applied strain is observed. After the knee-region, the stress increase continues at a smaller rate than in the elastic region. The most suitable phenomenon underlying the presence of a knee region is thought to be the initiation of matrix damage under the action of yarn re-orientation towards the applied load direction. In this case, this initiation occurs at lower stress levels than in the ‘folded’ specimens, since there is no edge region where the fibres are more oriented to the load direction, as happens for the ‘folded’ specimens. Instead, for the ‘cut’ specimens, the edges consist of fibre ends resulting from the specimen cutting, which yields a lack of fibre continuity in addition to the lack of a region of yarns more oriented to the applied load. At the end of the ‘knee’ region of the curve, a weak increase of the stress for an increasing applied strain is observed. This region of the curve was seen to be essentially constant for the ‘folded’ specimen, while it appears to be slightly ascending for the ‘cut specimens’. However, it is still a region where the largest yarn re-orientation takes place under the action of the applied tensile load. This region ends with the highest stress point of the diagram, that is reached at about a strain of 0.8% to 0.9%. The final segment of the stress-strain curve is of course a quick drop of the stress, that is indicative of the complete failure of the material.

Varying the specimens’ aspect ratio, as explained in the previous section, a noticeable change in the tensile response of the material is seen. In particular, by increasing the specimen’s aspect ratio, both the tensile modulus E_x and the maximum tensile stress increase accordingly. The occurrence of this effect is thought to be fully caused by the influence of the edge-regions on the mechanical behaviour of the braided composite. In fact, in these regions, there is an alteration of the fibre orientation with respect to inner regions of the braided reinforcement. Edge fibres are oriented at a smaller angle to the x-axis (coinciding with the tensile load axis and with the principal tensile and compressive stress direction under bending) with respect to the nominal 45°-orientation present in the laminate region away from the specimen edges. Together with this aspect, an additional element contributing to increase the principal tensile and bending moduli between the ‘cut’ and ‘folded’ specimens is the fibre continuity, that is preserved in the ‘folded’ specimens, while it is absent in the ‘cut’ specimens.

Table 1: Values of the measured tensile and flexural moduli of the specimens tested.

Specimens	Elastic modulus E_x [GPa]	Maximum stress [MPa]	Flexural Modulus [GPa]	Maximum bending moment A.R.=6.67 [Nm]
‘Cut’ material	13.0	125	17.2	53.2
‘Folded’ (A.R. 4)	20.6	156	22.9	-
‘Folded’ (A.R. 5)	22.3	217	23.6	-
‘Folded’ (A.R. 6.67)	25.8	310	39.4	126

In Figure 3(b) two load-displacement diagrams are shown, which represent the typical behaviour of folded and cut specimens of identical aspect ratio. The bending behaviour of these specimens is quantitatively different, but not qualitatively. In fact, under bending, the presence of uncut reinforcing fabric edges is only responsible for an increase in the materials bending moment contrasting the applied three-point bending load. This occurs as a result of the lower orientation of fibres in the edge regions. Values of the principal mechanical properties recorded for the specimens tested are listed in Table 1, in which the main differences among the different material structures may be numerically appreciated.

Figure 4. Experimental relationship between specimen aspect ratio and (a) the longitudinal E_x elastic modulus and (b) the flexural moduli of specimens tested.

The influence of the edges on the mechanical properties of the material can be quantitatively observed by plotting the elastic moduli values against the specimens' aspect ratio values. This is shown in Figure 4. Even if the cut specimens have been manufactured and tested with one only aspect ratio (nominally set to the value of 6.7), the cut material's properties as a function of the specimens' aspect ratio may reasonably be considered to be constant. On the contrary, the main aim of the present work was to produce experimental data on the elastic moduli change with the aspect ratio increase of the specimens with reinforcing braided fabric edges uncut. Both the diagrams reported in Figure 4 show that an increase in the specimens aspect ratio, corresponding to an increase of the edge regions volume with respect to the total material volume, causes the material's elastic moduli to increase accordingly. The development of an analytical model to theoretically represent such a dependence is currently being undertaken.

Failure Behaviour

Fibre continuity in the 'folded' specimens also has a remarkable influence on the failure behaviour of the material when compared to the 'cut' material. In both cases, tensile failure is accompanied by extensive matrix fracture and delaminations, with minimal fibre bundle breakage. However, while in the 'cut' specimens a length approximately equal to one specimen width is interested by material failure, in the 'folded' specimens the failure region spreads over a larger area (Figure 5). In particular, the specimen length interested by failure

increases with the specimen's aspect ratio. The failed area spread all over the specimen volume for the folded specimens with the highest aspect ratio (nominally valued 6.7): this is shown in Figure 5(d).

Figure 5. Sequence of pictures showing the extension of the tensile failure area in the different specimens tested. A failed area of increasing length is present in specimens of increasing aspect ratio.

- (a) cut specimen, A.R.=6.7, width=30mm;*
- (b) folded specimen, A.R.=4, width=50mm;*
- (c) folded specimen, A.R.=5, width=40mm;*
- (d) folded specimen, A.R.=6.7, width=30mm.*

The tensile failure is always accompanied by severe alteration of the composite reinforcement orientation angles in the failed area. In fact, the tensile straining of the composite specimens yields a re-adjustment of the material's structure, with a re-orientation of fibre bundles towards the applied load direction. In particular, the initial orientation of $\pm 45^\circ$ characterising the braided fabric is reduced to approximately $\pm 30^\circ$ after failure. This value can be shown to be in accordance with the predictions of the characteristic value of this braided fabric's locking angle [6].

Under a three-point bending load, material failure occurred in all cases as a compressive buckling of the outer compressed plies of the laminates. An image showing this damage is provided in Figure 6. After failure, all the specimens were characterised by a slight residual curvature due to the damage mentioned.

Figure 6. Detail showing the residual curvature and the compressive buckling characterising the bending failure of all the braided specimens (specimen width = 50mm). Pointed by arrows are the cotton yarns used for preform stitching.

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Tensile and three-point bending tests carried out on specimens of carbon fibre braided fabric reinforced epoxy resin specimens evidenced a strong influence of fabric edge regions on the response of the material to quasi-static mechanical loading. By varying the specimen aspect ratio the tests showed a reduction of material's tensile and flexural performance along with the reduction of the edge region extension in comparison to the specimen volume. This is mainly due to a higher orientation of the edge fibres in the preform towards the load direction compared to the nominal orientations characterising the braided fabric. The failure behaviour of the different specimens evidenced that the material region interested by the failure under simple tension increases in volume when the relative extension of the fabric edge region increases compared to the total specimen volume. The failure region eventually spreads over the whole material volume for specimen's aspect ratios higher than 6.7.

These findings may have a significant importance with regard to decisions made for design and manufacturing of braided composite structures. The choice of producing structural elements by using the reinforcing fabric edges or otherwise by cutting these will have to keep into consideration both the elastic performance achievable by the structure and the damage-

tolerance properties offered by either material's forms.

Immediate developments of the work described here will firstly include the definition of a theoretical model to describe the mechanical property change as a function of the specimen's (and hence of the actual structure's) aspect ratio. This is aimed at yielding a useful tool for designers to correctly calculate the architecture and dimensions of a braided reinforced composite structure.

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